

Figure S6. Changes in serum levels of the 20S proteasome and NEDD8

The changes in serum levels of the 20S proteasome (A) and NEDD8 (B) from before OFC to 2 h after OFC were compared between the OFC-positive and OFC-negative groups. * $p < 0.05$. In the OFC-negative group, one sample was excluded because enough serum was not available for the measurement.